

Kinetics and Mechanism of Substitution of Monovalent Anions in *cis* [Coen₂X₂]⁺ by Orthophenanthroline in Water-ethanol Mixture.

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The kinetics of the replacement of monovalent anions from *cis* [Coen₂X₂]⁺ (X⁻ = Cl⁻, CCl₃CO₂⁻, CHCl₂CO₂⁻, CH₂ClCO₂⁻ and CH₃CO₂⁻) by orthophenanthroline have been studied. The rate of replacement of the anions is independent of orthophenanthroline concentration and first order with respect to the complex concentration. The ease of displacement of the monovalent anion has been observed to be in the order

Thus it is observed that the lability of the outgoing anion increases as its basicity decreases. These facts suggest an S_N1 mechanism in which bond breaking by the leaving group is important in the transition state. The effect of ionic strength on the rate and the relative magnitude of other kinetic parameters ΔH[‡] and ΔS[‡] are in agreement with the S_N1 mechanism.

EXCHANGE reactions of unidentate ligand by unidentate ones in cobalt(III) complexes have been studied extensively and some generalisation have been made regarding the reaction mechanism. Bidentate-unidentate ligand exchange reactions have however not received similar attention. Little is known specially in the case of substitution reactions of unidentate ligands by bidentate ones in *cis* and *trans* cobalt(III) complexes of the type Co(AA)₂X₂ (AA = bidentate ligand, X = unidentate ligand), as to the difference of mechanism exhibited by two geometrical isomers leading to the formation of the same *cis* end product Co(AA)₂(yy) (yy=incoming bidentate ligand). The present study relates to the reaction

where en = ethylenediamine, *o*-phen = 1,10-phenanthroline and X⁻ = unidentate mono negative ligands Cl⁻, CCl₃CO₂⁻, CHCl₂CO₂⁻, CH₂ClCO₂⁻ and CH₃CO₂⁻. In the present paper, the study relates to *cis* series of compounds; those relating to *trans* series will be communicated subsequently. The reactions have been followed by measurements of specific conductivity at chosen temperatures of the reaction mixtures with desired

concentrations of the reacting complex and of the reagent *o*-phenanthroline in 30% alcohol-aqua medium according to the procedure given below.

Experimental

Materials: The complex *cis* [Coen₂Cl₂Cl, H₂O] was prepared by the method of J. C. Bailar, Jr.¹. The *cis* [Coen₂(RCO₂)₂]ClO₄ (R = CCl₃, CHCl₂, C[•]Cl, CH₃) complexes were prepared by the method of K. K. Kuroda and P. S. Gentile² with some modifications. After reaction with orthophenanthroline, the end products [Coen₂*o*-phen]Cl₃, [Coen₂*o*-phen]ClO₄, (CCl₃CO₂)₂, [Coen₂*o*-phen]ClO₄(CHCl₂CO₂)₂, [Coen₂*o*-phen]ClO₄(CH₂ClCO₂)₂ and [Coen₂*o*-phen]ClO₄(CH₃CO₂)₂ have been isolated by evaporating the solvents over steam bath and crystallization from different systems.

Cobalt in each of the reactant and product complexes was analyzed by converting the complex directly into cobalt(II) sulphate; nitrogen was estimated by semimicro combustion (Duma's method) as usual. The results of the analyses are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE REACTANT AND PRODUCT COMPLEXES

Complex	Analytical result			
	Found : Co. (%)	Calcd : Co (%)	Found : N (%)	Calcd : N (%)
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ Cl ₂]Cl, H ₂ O	19.27	19.43	18.41	18.46
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CCl ₃ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	9.42	9.77	8.92	9.29
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CHCl ₂ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	10.87	11.03	10.50	10.48
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CH ₂ ClCO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	12.25	12.66	11.75	12.03
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CH ₃ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	14.73	14.86	14.20	14.12
[Coen ₂ <i>o</i> -phen]Cl ₃	12.49	12.66	17.95	18.04
[Coen ₂ <i>o</i> -phen]ClO ₄ (CCl ₃ CO ₂) ₂	7.39	7.52	10.65	10.72
[Coen ₂ <i>o</i> -phen]ClO ₄ (CHCl ₂ CO ₂) ₂	8.18	8.24	11.52	11.75
[Coen ₂ <i>o</i> -phen]ClO ₄ (CH ₂ ClCO ₂) ₂	9.01	9.13	13.29	13.01
[Coen ₂ <i>o</i> -phen]ClO ₄ (CH ₃ CO ₂) ₂	10.05	10.22	14.47	14.57

The configuration of the reactant and product complexes was characterized from the UV absorption bands recorded in literature^{3,4,5} for aqueous solution at room temperature. The results have been shown in Table 2. Chemicals of analar quality were used in all experiments. The solutions of orthophenanthroline and the complex of desired concentrations were prepared freshly each time by dissolving calculated amounts in 30% ethanol for the kinetic studies.

The kinetic runs were conducted with orthophenanthroline concentration varied over the range 0.0125M-0.1250M and at constant ionic strength. The results obtained are presented in Table 3.

It is observed that the pseudo first order rate constant (for a particular complex) is independent of orthophenanthroline concentration. The rate expression for these reactions can therefore be represented as rate = k₁

TABLE 2—ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF REACTANT AND PRODUCT COMPLEXES.

Complex	Literature values/ observed values	1st band		2nd band		3rd band	
		λ max in nm	log ε	λ max in nm	log ε	λ max in nm	log ε
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ Cl ₃] ⁺	Lit. values ³	540	2.00	390	1.89	240	4.28
	obs. values	540	1.99	388	1.90	240	4.26
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ (CCl ₃ CO ₂) ₃] ⁺	Lit. values ⁴	497	2.10	361	1.94	226	4.34
	obs. values	497	2.10	361	1.95	226	4.30
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ (CHCl ₂ CO ₂) ₃] ⁺	Lit. values ⁴	498	2.09	361	1.94	225	4.32
	obs. values	499	2.10	362	1.96	225	4.30
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ (CH ₂ ClCO ₂) ₃] ⁺	Lit. values ⁵	502	2.13	361	1.96	228	4.30
	obs. values	502	2.14	362	1.98	228	4.33
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ (CH ₃ CO ₂) ₃] ⁺	Lit. values ⁴	506	2.17	362	1.98	228	4.29
	obs. values	503	2.12	362	1.94	227	4.22
[Coen ₃ <i>o</i> -phen] ³⁺	Lit. values ⁵	470	2.07	352	2.88	275	4.51
	obs. values	470	2.08	352	2.90	273	4.52

Instruments : The spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer. Conductivity measurements were made with a conductivity bridge model R.C. 16B2 (made by Industrial Instruments, USA). The thermostat was accurate to ± 0.1°C.

Procedure : Equal volumes of solutions of orthophenanthroline and the complex of desired concentrations were taken in the reaction vessel, kept at the desired temperature. Using a dip type conductivity cell, specific conductances were noted at constant time interval Δ t during the course of reaction and it was possible to evaluate pseudo first order rate constant graphically by the Guggenheim⁶ method by plotting log₁₀(λ'-λ) vs the time t, where λ and λ' were specific conductance values at time t and time t + Δ t respectively.

Results and Discussion

In one series of experiments, the effect of varying the *o*-phen concentration on the reaction rate was measured.

[complex]. Further it is evident from the Table 3 that rates vary markedly with the nature of the group being replaced. The order of the rates of replacement being

which is the same as the order of increasing basicity of the outgoing ligands. It is customary to assume that the order of increasing basicity of ligands is also the order of increasing metal-ligand bond strengths. These facts indicate that bond breaking is important in the activated state and suggest a dissociative mechanism for the reactions studied.

Second step is many times faster than the first step since the nonflexible orthophenanthroline molecule (unlike oxalate⁷ ion) after attaching itself to the five coordinated intermediate closes the chelate ring rapidly with simultaneous rupture of second Co-X bond. That both X⁻

TABLE 3—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR REACTION OF THE *cis* [Coen₃X₂]⁺ IONS WITH ORTHOPHENANTHROLINE (X⁻ = Cl⁻, CCl₃CO₂⁻, CHCl₂CO₂⁻, CH₂ClCO₂⁻, CH₃CO₂⁻).

Temp. (°C)	Complex	Concn. of complex	Concn. of <i>o</i> -phen	Ionic strength	Specific reaction rate (in hr ⁻¹)
36	<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ Cl ₃]Cl	0.005 M	0.1250 M	0.005	2.49
"	"	"	0.0625 M	"	2.43
"	"	"	0.0250 M	"	2.34
60	<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ (CCl ₃ CO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	0.0025 M	0.1250 M	0.0025	2.34
"	"	"	0.0125 M	"	1.13
60	<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ (CHCl ₂ CO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	0.0025 M	0.1250 M	0.0025	1.11
"	"	"	0.0125 M	"	0.90
60	<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ (CH ₂ ClCO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	0.0025 M	0.1250 M	0.0025	0.90
"	"	"	0.0125 M	"	0.88
65	<i>cis</i> [Coen ₃ (CH ₃ CO ₂) ₃]ClO ₄	0.0020 M	0.1250 M	0.0020	0.88
"	"	"	0.0125 M	"	0.046
"	"	"	"	"	0.046

ions are released almost simultaneously by reaction with orthophenanthroline is strongly indicated by the following facts: (a) The end product is always $[\text{Coen}_2 \text{ o-phen}]^{3+}$ as indicated by the chemical analysis and the spectral characterisation of the end product. There is no evidence of any stable intermediate product being formed. (b) The Guggenheim plot $\log(\lambda_{t+\Delta t} - \lambda_t)$ vs time yields a straight line from the start upto the stage to which the reaction has been followed in each case. Had there been any stable or unstable intermediate formed during the course of the reaction the slope of the plot would have gradually changed as the intermediate would have released X^- at a rate different from the original complex and the straight line plot would not have been obtained. (c) Each reaction has been followed to a stage of three-fourth completion as indicated from the end value of the specific conductance at this stage.

In a second set of experiments, orthophenanthroline concentration was kept constant at 0.125 M, the ionic strength was varied over the range 0.00125-0.01 by varying the complex salt concentration. The values of specific reaction rate k_1 at different ionic strength are shown in Table 4. It is evident from Table 4 that the rate of reaction in each case is increased with the increase in ionic strength except in the case of bis acetato complex. This influence of ionic strength on the rate is in accord with S_N1 mechanism in which net charge on the cation is increased by dissociation at the rate determining step. The determination of net charge on the activated intermediate has been attempted.

Assuming a dissociative mechanism, the thermodynamic equilibrium constant for the pre-reaction equilibrium between the reactant complex and the active unstable intermediate

$$\text{Conc. C} \quad \text{Conc. C}^* \quad \text{Conc. C}_X$$

is given by $K = \frac{C^* \cdot C_X^{n+1} \cdot f^* \cdot f_X^n}{Cf}$, the f 's denoting the respective activity co-efficients.

At equilibrium, forward and backward reaction rates are equal and hence $k_1 C = k_{-1} C^* C_X^n$. Combining the above two equations we have

$$k_1 = \frac{k_0 f}{f^* f_X^n} \text{ where } k_0 = k_{-1} K$$

taking logarithms and using the Debye Huckel limiting law

$$-\log f_i = AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu} \text{ where } A = \frac{1.82 \times 10^6}{(DT)^{3/2}} \quad (D = \text{dielectric constant of the medium}), Z_i \text{ is the charge of the species } i \text{ and } \mu \text{ is the ionic strength of the reaction medium, we have } \log k_1 = \log \frac{k_0}{f^*} + (n^2 + 3n) A \sqrt{\mu}.$$

Therefore the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ should give straight line with slope $A(n^2 + 3n)$.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION OF THE CIS $[\text{Coen}_2\text{X}_2]^+$ IONS ($X^- = \text{Cl}^-, \text{CCl}_3\text{CO}_2^-, \text{CHCl}_2\text{CO}_2^-, \text{CH}_2\text{ClCO}_2^-, \text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2^-$) WITH ORTHOPHENANTHROLINE (0.125 M).

Complex	Concn. of complex	Ionic strength μ	$\sqrt{\mu}$	Specific reaction rate k_1	$\log k_1$
<i>cis</i> $[\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ at 36°C	0.01000 M	0.01000	0.100	2.86 hr ⁻¹	0.456
	0.00830 M	0.00830	0.091	2.76 hr ⁻¹	0.441
	0.00500 M	0.00500	0.071	2.49 hr ⁻¹	0.396
	0.00250 M	0.00250	0.050	2.28 hr ⁻¹	0.358
<i>cis</i> $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{CCl}_3\text{CO}_2)_2]$ ClO ₄ at 60°C	0.01000 M	0.01000	0.100	1.35 hr ⁻¹	0.130
	0.00500 M	0.00500	0.071	1.22 hr ⁻¹	0.086
	0.00250 M	0.00250	0.050	1.13 hr ⁻¹	0.053
	0.00125 M	0.00125	0.035	1.03 hr ⁻¹	0.013
<i>cis</i> $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{CHCl}_2\text{CO}_2)_2]$ ClO ₄ at 60°C	0.01000 M	0.01000	0.100	1.10 hr ⁻¹	0.041
	0.00500 M	0.00500	0.071	0.99 hr ⁻¹	-0.004
	0.00250 M	0.00250	0.050	0.90 hr ⁻¹	-0.046
	0.00125 M	0.00125	0.035	0.84 hr ⁻¹	-0.076
<i>cis</i> $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{CH}_2\text{ClCO}_2)_2]$ ClO ₄ at 60°C	0.01000 M	0.01000	0.100	1.06 hr ⁻¹	0.025
	0.00500 M	0.00500	0.071	0.97 hr ⁻¹	-0.013
	0.00250 M	0.00250	0.050	0.88 hr ⁻¹	-0.056
	0.00125 M	0.00125	0.035	0.82 hr ⁻¹	-0.086
<i>cis</i> $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_2]$ ClO ₄ at 60°C	0.01000 M	0.01000	0.100	0.046 hr ⁻¹	-1.337
	0.00200 M	0.00200	0.045	0.046 hr ⁻¹	-1.337

It is found that plots of $\log k_1$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ are practically straight lines. The slopes of these straight lines $A(n^2 + 3n)$ and values of $1+n$, the charge on the activated complex are presented in Table 5. The values of A in Table 5 were determined by measuring the dielectric constant D of the reaction medium with the help of a Q-Meter.

does not dissociate at all before being attacked by orthophenanthroline. In these studies μ is maintained < 0.01 , since at $\mu > 0.01$ the simple Debye-Huckel theory fails to predict activity coefficient of ions.

In third series of experiments the temperature effect on the reaction rate was determined by running experi-

TABLE 5—EVALUATION OF NET CHARGE ON THE ACTIVATED STATE FOR THE REACTION OF *cis* [Coen₂X₁][±] IONS WITH ORTHOPHENANTHROLINE (X⁻ = Cl⁻, CCl₃CO₂⁻, CHCl₂CO₂⁻, CH₂ClCO₂⁻).

Complex	Temp. T (°K)	Dielectric constant of the medium	Values of A	Slope A(n ² +3n)	Values of n	Charge on the activated state (1+n)
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	309	56.5	0.79	2.00	0.69	1.69
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CCl ₃ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	333	49.0	0.87	1.80	0.58	1.58
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CHCl ₂ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	333	49.0	0.87	1.75	0.56	1.56
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CH ₂ ClCO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	333	49.0	0.87	1.70	0.55	1.55

These results indicate that the net charge on the complex cations (except in diacetato complex where k_1 is independent of μ . Table 4) is increased in the activated state. The values span a range between +1.55 to +1.69. Thus the path of the reaction no doubt involves dissociation of the complex, but the fractional charge on the activated complex is an indication that in the activated state the penta coordinated doubly charged complex forms an ion pair with the anion X⁻. Finally in the case of Coen₂(CH₃CO₂)₂⁻ ion, constant k_1 is independent of the ionic strength (Table 4). This indicates that in the case of the diacetato complex, the charge +1 of the reactant remains the same (+1) in the activated state i. e. the activated ion pair.

ments at different temperature (Table 6). It was found that plots of $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$ are practically straight lines. The values of the activation enthalpy ΔH_1^\ddagger , and entropy of activation ΔS_1^\ddagger (Table 7) were calculated from the slopes and intercept, respectively of the $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$ plots, using the Eyring equation⁹.

It will be seen from Table 7 that the activation enthalpy ΔH_1^\ddagger increases as basicity of the leaving group X⁻ increases in the series

Indeed the parallelism between the acid dissociation constants K_a for the acids HX and activation enthalpies ΔH_1^\ddagger for the substitution reactions with leaving group

TABLE 6—INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE ON REACTION RATE.

Complex	Temp. (in Abs.)	k_1 (in hr ⁻¹)	Conditions of experiment
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	294°	0.48	[Coen ₂ Cl ₂]Cl concentration = 0.0083 M; <i>o</i> -phen. concentration = 0.125 M ionic strength = 0.0083.
	299°	0.90	
	304°	1.75	
	309°	2.76	
	314°	4.93	
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CCl ₃ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	318°	0.22	[Coen ₂ (CCl ₃ CO ₂) ₂] ClO ₄ concentration = 0.0025 M <i>o</i> -phen. concentration = 0.125 M, ionic strength = 0.0025.
	323°	0.35	
	328°	0.68	
	333°	1.13	
	338°	1.82	
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CHCl ₂ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	318°	0.19	[Coen ₂ (CHCl ₂ CO ₂) ₂] ClO ₄ concentration = 0.0025 M <i>o</i> -phen. concentration = 0.125 M, ionic strength = 0.0025.
	323°	0.30	
	328°	0.55	
	333°	0.90	
	338°	1.52	
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CH ₂ ClCO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	318°	0.17	[Coen ₂ (CH ₂ ClCO ₂) ₂] ClO ₄ concentration = 0.0025 M <i>o</i> -phen. concentration = 0.125 M, ionic strength = 0.0025.
	323°	0.29	
	328°	0.53	
	333°	0.88	
	338°	1.51	
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CH ₃ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	338°	0.046	[Coen ₂ (CH ₃ CO ₂) ₂] ClO ₄ concentration = 0.002 M <i>o</i> -phen. concentration = 0.125 M, ionic strength = 0.002.
	341°	0.081	
	345°	0.126	

TABLE 7—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS.

Complex	Average Temp. (°C)	ΔH_1^\ddagger KCal mole ⁻¹	ΔS_1^\ddagger e.u.	Acid dissociation constant ⁹ K_a at 25°C for HX (X ⁻ = leaving group).
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	31	21.3	-3.5	large
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CCl ₂ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	55	22.3	-7.5	2.0 × 10 ⁻¹
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CHClCO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	55	22.7	-8.0	5.0 × 10 ⁻²
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CH ₂ ClCO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	55	23.5	-5.6	1.4 × 10 ⁻²
<i>cis</i> [Coen ₂ (CH ₃ CO ₂) ₂]ClO ₄	68.5	30.6	+8.9	1.8 × 10 ⁻⁵

X⁻ is excellent. This provides a good evidence in favour of a dissociative mechanism which involves C₀-X bond breaking; the stronger the C₀-X bond with increasing basicity of X⁻ the higher is the energy required to break the bond to yield pentacoordinated activated state. Similar trends have been found in the (acid and base hydrolysis reaction of Co(NH₃)₅X²⁺ X⁻ = CCl₃CO₂⁻, CHCl₂CO₂⁻, CH₂ClCO₂⁻, CH₃CO₂⁻ etc.), where the rate constants k_{H_2O} and k_{OH^-} decrease with increase in basicity of X⁻. The authors have assigned a dissociative S_N1 mechanism for these reactions leading to the formation of pentacoordinated intermediate by breaking the C₀-X bond.

It will also be observed from Table 7 that except in the case of Coen₂(CH₃CO₂)₂⁺ the reactions of all other complexes studied exhibit negative entropies of activation of the order of -5 e.u. This is expected in a dissociative mechanism Coen₂X₂⁺ → Coen₂X²⁺ + X⁻ where the activated intermediate has a greater charge and is solvated more than the reactant complex and where the released charged ions X⁻ also get solvated. The above two electrostriction effect are presumably responsible for the negative entropy of activation.

In the case of Coen₂(CH₃CO₂)₂⁺ ion however entropy of activation is positive. This is consistent with the formation of the ion pair {[Coen₂(CH₃CO₂)₂]²⁺·CH₃CO₂⁻]¹⁺ which has the same charge as the reacting complex and does not release any acetate

ion in solution so that there is practically no electrostriction. On the otherhand the greater size of the ion pair causes greater disturbance to the solvent structure leading to rupture of many of the solvent intermolecular bonds and thus causing a greater entropy of activation. Also the structure of the ion pair is less tight than the reactant complex and this also contributes to positive entropy of activation.

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